

Supplementary information to:

The impact of operation flexibility, equipment flexibility, and material handling flexibility on the design of matrix-structured manufacturing systems

Patrick Schumacher*, Christian Weckenborg*, Thomas S. Spengler*

* *Institute of Automotive Management and Industrial Production, Technische Universität Braunschweig, Mühlenpfordtstraße 23, 38106 Braunschweig, Germany (Tel: +49 531 391 2212; e-mail: {[p.schumacher](mailto:p.schumacher@tu-braunschweig.de), [c.weckenborg](mailto:c.weckenborg@tu-braunschweig.de), [t.spengler](mailto:t.spengler@tu-braunschweig.de)}@tu-braunschweig.de).*

The following model formulation is a modified version of the model presented in Schumacher et al. (2021) and was implemented in Python 3.9 and was used to solve the numerical examples presented in the above mentioned contribution by using the Python Gurobi API (version 9.1.0). The computations were run on a standard computer with AMD Ryzen 7 PRO 3700U CPU @ 2.3 GHz and 32 GB RAM.

Table 1 General notation of sets, parameters and decision variables

<i>Sets and parameters</i>	
P	Set of products (index p)
R	Set of resources (index r, s, t)
L	Set of locations (index l, l')
O	Set of operations (index o, q, u)
O_p	Set of operations of product p
N_p	Number of different routes of product p (index n)
$a_{r,o}$	1, if resource r can perform operation o ; 0, otherwise
$\beta_{r,o,p}$	Processing time of resource r on operation o for product p
ic	Cost rate induced by opening a location
c_r	Cost rate induced by resource r
ct	Cost rate for material transport
$d_{l,l'}$	Distance between locations l and l'
K	Maximum number of resources to be assigned to each production cell
Q	Maximum time for resources to execute operations
D_p	Demand of product p
e_{oqn}^p	1, if operation o precedes operation q in route n ; 0, otherwise
<i>Decision and derived variables</i>	
x_l	1, if the station at location l is opened; 0, otherwise
$y_{l,r}$	1, if resource r is assigned to the station at location l ; 0, otherwise
$y_{l,r,l',s}$	1, if resource r is assigned to the station at location l and resource s is assigned to the station at location l' ; 0, otherwise
v_{orqspn}	Flow of units of product p from operation o performed by resource r to operation q performed by resource s on route n
f_{pn}	Number of units of product p assigned to route n
$t_{l,r,l',s}$	Number of units of products transported from location l to location l'

Minimize

$$\sum_{l=1}^L x_l \cdot ic + \sum_{r=1}^R \sum_{l=1}^L y_{l,r} \cdot c_r + \sum_{r=1}^R \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{s=1}^R \sum_{l'=1}^L ct \cdot d_{ll'} \cdot t_{l,r,l',s} \quad (1)$$

Subject to:

$$\sum_{r=1}^R y_{l,r} \leq K \cdot x_l \quad \forall l \in \{1, \dots, L\} \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{l=1}^L y_{l,r} \leq 1 \quad \forall r \in \{1, \dots, R\} \quad (3)$$

$$y_{l,r,l',s} \leq y_{l,r} \quad \forall l \in \{1, \dots, L\}, l' \in \{1, \dots, L\}, r \in \{1, \dots, R\}, s \in \{1, \dots, R\} \quad (4)$$

$$y_{l,r,l',s} \leq y_{l',s} \quad \forall l \in \{1, \dots, L\}, l' \in \{1, \dots, L\}, r \in \{1, \dots, R\}, s \in \{1, \dots, R\} \quad (5)$$

$$y_{l,r,l',s} \geq y_{l,r} + y_{l',s} - 1 \quad \forall l \in \{1, \dots, L\}, l' \in \{1, \dots, L\}, r \in \{1, \dots, R\}, s \in \{1, \dots, R\} \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{N_p} \sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{r=1}^R \sum_{o=1}^{O_p} \sum_{q=1}^{O_p} v_{orqspn} \cdot \beta_{s,q,p} \leq Q \quad \forall s \in \{1, \dots, R\} \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{N_p} \sum_{p=1}^P v_{orqspn} \leq a_{r,o} \cdot a_{s,q} \cdot \sum_{l=1}^L \sum_{l'=1}^L y_{l,r,l',s} \cdot \sum_{p=1}^P D_p \quad \forall r \in \{1, \dots, R\}, s \in \{1, \dots, R\}, o \in \{1, \dots, O_p\}, q \in \{1, \dots, O_p\}, o \neq q \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_{r=1}^R \sum_{s=1}^R v_{orqspn} = f_{pn} \cdot e_{oqn}^p \quad \forall q \in \{1, \dots, O_p\}, o \in \{1, \dots, O_p\}, o \neq q, p \in \{1, \dots, P\}, n \in \{1, \dots, N_p\} \quad (9)$$

$$D_p = \sum_{n=1}^{N_p} f_{pn} \quad \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\} \quad (10)$$

$$\sum_{r=1}^R \sum_{o=1}^{O_p} v_{orqspn} = \sum_{l=1}^R \sum_{r=1}^{O_p} v_{qsutpn} \quad \forall q \in \{1, \dots, O_p\}, s \in \{1, \dots, R\}, p \in \{1, \dots, P\}, n \in \{1, \dots, N_p\} \quad (11)$$

$$t_{l,r,l',s} \leq y_{l,r,l',s} \cdot \sum_{p=1}^P D_p \quad \forall l \in \{1, \dots, L\}, l' \in \{1, \dots, L\}, r \in \{1, \dots, R\}, s \in \{1, \dots, R\} \quad (12)$$

$$t_{l,r,l',s} \leq \sum_{n=1}^{N_p} \sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{o=1}^{O_p} \sum_{q=1}^{O_p} v_{orqspn} \quad \forall l \in \{1, \dots, L\}, l' \in \{1, \dots, L\}, r \in \{1, \dots, R\}, s \in \{1, \dots, R\} \quad (13)$$

$$t_{l,r,l',s} \geq \sum_{n=1}^{N_p} \sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{o=1}^{O_p} \sum_{q=1}^{O_p} v_{orqspn} - (1 - y_{l,r,l',s}) \cdot \sum_{p=1}^P D_p \quad \forall l \in \{1, \dots, L\}, l' \in \{1, \dots, L\}, r \in \{1, \dots, R\}, s \in \{1, \dots, R\} \quad (14)$$

$$x_l \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall l \in \{1, \dots, L\} \quad (15)$$

$$y_{l,r} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall l \in \{1, \dots, L\}, r \in \{1, \dots, R\} \quad (16)$$

$$y_{l,r,l',s} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall l \in \{1, \dots, L\}, l' \in \{1, \dots, L\}, r \in \{1, \dots, R\}, s \in \{1, \dots, R\} \quad (17)$$

$$v_{orqspn} \geq 0 \quad \forall q \in \{1, \dots, O_p\}, o \in \{1, \dots, O_p\}, o \neq q, p \in \{1, \dots, P\}, r \in \{1, \dots, R\}, s \in \{1, \dots, R\}, n \in \{1, \dots, N_p\} \quad (18)$$

$$f_{pn} \geq 0 \quad \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}, n \in \{1, \dots, N_p\} \quad (19)$$

$$t_{l,r,l',s} \geq 0 \quad \forall l \in \{1, \dots, L\}, l' \in \{1, \dots, L\}, r \in \{1, \dots, R\}, s \in \{1, \dots, R\} \quad (20)$$

Objective (1) is to minimize the total costs of the initial configuration of a MMS. The total costs consist of the costs for opened stations, the costs for resources, and the transportation costs. Constraints (2) guarantee that resources can only be assigned to opened stations and that the maximum number of resources per station is complied with. Constraints (3) ensure that every resource is assigned to upmost one station. Constraints (4) – (6) link the decision variables $y_{l,r}$ to the auxiliary variables $y_{l,r,l',s}$. Constraints (7) ensure that the workload assigned to each resource is less than the maximum time for resources to execute operations. Constraints (8) assure that operations can only be assigned to resources that are deployed and capable of executing the specific operation. Constraints (9) link the variables f_{pn} and v_{orqspn} . Constraints (10) guarantee demand fulfillment for every product and Constraints (11) ensure flow balance for every resource. Constraints (12) – (14) link the transport variables $t_{l,r,l',s}$ to the flow variables v_{orqspn} . Finally, constraints (15) – (20) define the domains of the decision variables.

Publication bibliography

Schumacher, Patrick; Weckenborg, Christian; Spengler, Thomas S. (2021): Economic Design of Matrix-Structured Manufacturing Systems. In Alexandre Dolgui, Alain Bernard, David Lemoine, Gregor von Cieminski, David Romero (Eds.): Advances in Production Management Systems. Artificial Intelligence for Sustainable and Resilient Production Systems, vol. 631. Cham: Springer International Publishing (IFIP Advances in Information and Communication Technology), pp. 516–524.